

The Role of Military-Recreational Tourism in Solving Socio-Economic Problems

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Abstract: In economically developed countries of the world, the tourism industry occupies a leading position in the economy, and its level of development, dynamics, technological, structural and other characteristics have a certain impact on economic and social progress, and the position of countries in the global world. The tourism industry in the world is developing rapidly, ranking third in terms of GDP, behind the oil industry and the automotive industry. This to some extent defines the service sector as the leading sector of the economy of developed countries.

Keywords: military recreational tourism, military recreational and tourist activities, tourism potential, socio-economic development of the country

Introduction. Uzbekistan has set specific goals: "becoming one of the countries with an above-average income through sustainable economic development, creating a system of education, medicine and social protection that fully meets the needs of the people and international standards, favorable environmental conditions for the population, guaranteed ensuring the sovereignty and security of the country". In this regard, we note that one of the promising types of the tourism industry, which can become a catalyst for the economic development of the country, solving social problems, ensuring the security of the country, increasing the sense of patriotism among the population, especially among young people, is military recreation. The improvement of this area is a priority in the development of domestic tourism with the systematic involvement of all categories of the population, with special emphasis on children's and youth recreation.

Currently, the priority areas of research in the field of development and promotion of military recreational services on a global scale are: the formation of a theoretical basis for military recreational activities, the development of methodological foundations for the analysis and evaluation of military recreational territories and resources, a comprehensive assessment of the impact of military recreational activities on the sectoral system of the country's economy.

The purpose of the study is to develop scientific proposals and practical recommendations on the activation of military recreation as a factor in ensuring socio-economic stability.

Research objectives:

- analysis of the conceptual and terminological apparatus of the military-recreational-tourism sphere;
- to analyze the institutional basis for the development of tourism, recreational and military-recreational tourism activities and develop scientific proposals for its improvement;
- to study the theoretical foundations of the activation of military recreational and tourist activities in the context of ensuring socio-economic stability;

- analysis of world experience in the development of military recreational and tourist activities;
- assessment and analysis of the problems of the socio-economic situation of military personnel and determination of the possibilities of the military-recreational-tourist sphere in their elimination;
- identification of problematic aspects in the diversification of recreational and tourist services;
- substantiation of the socio-economic importance and the need to develop conceptual foundations for the development of the military-recreational-tourism sector through the prism of preparing the population for threats;
- study of the possibilities and ways of popularization of the military recreational and tourist sphere among young people with the development of children's and youth recreation;
- determination of the impact of the effectiveness of the use of military recreational and tourist potential on the country's economy.

Analysis and results.

The socio-economic development of the country is directly related to which people will replace the previous generation. Of course, every component takes place here: energy, youth activity, intellectual and educational components, physical health, ideological stability, patriotism, etc.

The analysis of the conceptual and terminological apparatus of recreational tourism and military recreational tourism activities (MRTA) is carried out. One of the distinguishing aspects of the research of the terminological apparatus of the MRTA in developed countries from research in the post-Soviet space is the fact that the issues of military recreation are solved quite seriously there, although the theoretical component still needs serious scientific research. The modern world order creates a demand for the development of "military recreation", so, for example, Washington State has developed a program for reporting to the Ministry of Defense on the implementation of its strategic plans, including recommendations on how the state can contribute to the preservation of military missions and capacity expansion.

The work on this report is carried out by leading specialists, theoretical specialists in various fields, including specialists in the field of MRTA (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The structural basis of the impact of military recreational activities on the socio-economic development of the country.

Based on the above, the following definition of the term "military recreation" is proposed – the restoration of the physical and spiritual forces of personnel spent during service in the system of military and paramilitary structures, rehabilitation, patriotic education and arming youth with survival skills in various conditions.

This definition fully reflects the very specifics of "military recreation", which covers the social component of the service process, which, in turn, is directly related to the effectiveness and quality of service. At the same time, it should be noted that "military recreation" also performs the function of physical, spiritual and patriotic preparation of the population for various threats.

It is established that the "recreational potential" is based on two basic resources – recreational resources and socio-economic resources. The author's analysis of foreign literature (including CIS countries), as well as domestic studies, is also interesting, which showed that the issues of classification of the military-recreational and military-tourist potential of the region are indeed poorly studied (the leading journals included in authoritative databases have been studied). In this regard, there is a need to develop a classification of the military-recreational and military-tourist potential of the region. At the same time, based on the purpose of the study, it was decided to develop a unified classification of the military, recreational and tourist potential of the region (Fig.2).

Figure 2. The structural basis of the classification of the military-recreational-tourist potential of the country

To begin with, it became necessary to clarify the very concept of "military-recreational-tourist potential". So, the author proposed the following definition: "military recreational and tourist potential" is the availability and quality of military recreational infrastructure, military recreational resources, military historical resources, the use of which is aimed at organizing and preparing primary military and physical training of the population (including children and adolescents), restoring health in during the service (including various diseases and moral and psychological problems) (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Classification of the influence of the military recreation and tourism sector (MRTA) on the socio-economic development of the country and its armed forces.

The mechanism of development of the concept of military recreational activities involves its implementation in three stages:

The first stage includes an analysis of the history of the development of military recreational activities in the region, which is a prerequisite for starting work.

The second stage includes the definition of the principles of the development of this concept, which should reflect a clear position on issues of socio-economic balance, sustainable development of the territory, the availability of opportunities for both enterprises and consumers, an environmentally friendly environment that is interconnected with the national interests of the people.

At the third stage, the issues of creating a regulatory framework, information support, tax regulation, an innovative approach to creating a military-recreational image of the region and other opportunities are considered.

The result of all these measures and actions is the developed target program of the region aimed at the development of military recreational activities, which would become a condition for the sustainable development of the region (implemented on the basis of comprehensive programs for the development of military recreational activities, both at the republican and at the level of a specific military recreational zone). The above-mentioned processes need constant monitoring of the progress of the set goal, its possible deviations from the planned course with the possibility of returning to the main action strategy.

Conclusion:

In order to consolidate the basic principles of military recreation, involving the implementation of a set of measures to prevent socio-economic, spiritual and political threats with an emphasis on educating a harmoniously developed young generation and promoting a healthy lifestyle and active recreation, the need for amendments to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been proved, which would consolidate the state's obligations to create conditions "for intellectual creative, physical and moral formation and development of youth, the realization of their rights to education, health, housing, employment, employment and recreation".

Based on the analysis of modern trends in the development of society and changes in the structure of recreational and military-recreational needs, the Concept of military sports recreation is proposed, contributing to the consolidation of such government structures as: the Ministry of Youth Policy and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Agency for Youth Affairs, the Ministry of Mahalla Support and the Older Generation, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher Education education, science and innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in solving complex tasks for the development of children's and youth recreation, as well as physical, spiritual and patriotic training of youth.

In order to develop and diversify recreational and tourist services, improve the quality of labor resources by strengthening public health and ensuring safety, it is necessary to adopt the Concept of Sustainable development of recreational and tourist activities in Uzbekistan.

The above-mentioned scientific proposals and practical recommendations serve to improve the organizational, economic and methodological directions of the development of the military-recreational sphere.

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